

Sensing of ammonia by electrically conducting polyaniline - MoS₂ nanocomposites

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ABSTRACT

Nanocomposites of polyaniline and molybdenum disulphide (MoS₂) were synthesized by oxidative polymerization. The synthesized nanocomposites were characterized by Ultraviolet-Visible (UV-Vis) spectroscopy, Fourier Transform Infrared spectroscopy (FTIR), Electron Microscopy (SEM), and X-ray diffraction (XRD). Morphology of the nanocomposites revealed the incorporation of PANI on the surface and in between the layers of exfoliated MoS₂. The nanocomposites were studied for electrical conductivity. Semiconducting nature of the nanocomposites was revealed. The sensing behavior of the nanocomposites towards Hydrogen sulphide was studied.

Keywords: Polyaniline, MoS₂, Nanocomposites, electrical conductivity, sensor

1. INTRODUCTION

Polyaniline is highly conducting in the emeraldine form. The conductivity can reach upto 10³ to 10⁵ S cm⁻¹. PANI can be reversibly doped/dedoped, by acids or bases, owing to its redox chemistry. Compared to other conducting polymers, PANI possesses high stability.

In its emeraldine salt form, it exhibits excellent electrical conductivity, where as in the emeraldine base form, i.e the dedoped form, it is non-conducting. The switching of PANI in conducting and non-conducting forms by doping with acid makes it a choice of sensor. Varying conductivity in varying atmospheres makes PANI a sensor to sense several gases. PANI acts as sensor to sense gases like ammonia, oxides of nitrogen, volatile organic compounds etc.

Nature of dopant also affects the electrical conductivity of PANI, hence, PANI doped with various dopants is a promising material for sensing various types of molecules.¹

Molybdenum disulfide (MoS_2) is a two dimensional layered structure, in which various layers are stacked over each other. A monolayer of MoS_2 have planes of sulfide ions in which Molybdenum atom is sandwiched. In bulk MoS_2 several monolayers are stacked over one another, by weak van der waals interactions. Bulk MoS_2 is diamagnetic compound with a band gap of 1.23eV, whereas monolayer MoS_2 has band gap of 1.8eV^{2,3}. It has excellent optical and electrical properties. This makes it a suitable material for transistor, photodetector and optoelectronic devices.

H_2S is widely used in chemical industries and research. The gas is highly flammable, poisonous and explosive in nature. It affects respiratory system. High exposure to the gas leads to several health hazards and can be fatal. Toxicity results in corneal injury and burns on skin. Damage of epithelium of respiratory track, alimentary canal, and chronic lung diseases. Due to its toxic nature, H_2S should be handled with care. The sensing of H_2S is a prominent area of research.

PANI improves the conductivity and stability of MoS_2 , and is used in synthesis of nanocomposites of PANI- MoS_2 nanocomposites. Pani- MoS_2 nanocomposites exhibited high sensitivity towards chloramphenicol and super capacitors made of such nanocomposites exhibited better performance. Considering these facts, we utilized PANI- MoS_2 nanocomposite for sensing H_2S vapors. We prepared PANI and PANI- MoS_2 nanocomposites to study the synergistic effect in electrical conductivity, stability and sensing ability.

2. MATERIAL and METHOD

2.1. Materials

Aniline (Merck), Molybdenum disulphide (CDH, India), potassium persulphate(CDH, India), Cetyl trimethyl ammonium bromide (CTAB) (CDH, India), HCl (Merck) were used as obtained. Double distilled water was used in the process.

2.2. Preparation of PANI- MoS_2 nanocomposites

A series of nanocomposites containing PANI, MoS_2 was prepared (table 1). A reaction mixture containing aniline, CTAB and MoS_2 in 1000ml HCl was sonicated for 30 min at 4-8°C. Potassium persulphate was added as oxidant

and the reaction was continued for 1 hour . After one hour, the reaction mixture was kept in refrigerator for overnight. The nanocomposites thus formed was filtered, washed with double distilled water and ethanol, dedoped with aqueous ammonia solution. Redoped with HCl, and dried in an air oven. Thus prepared PANI-MoS₂ nanocomposites were stored for further experiment.

TABLE 1: Details of PANI-MoS₂ nanocomposites synthesis.

Sample Code	MoS ₂	CTAB	Aniline	K ₂ S ₂ O ₈
PANI	0mole	0.01 mole	0.1 mole	0.05 mole
A1	0.001 mole	0.01 mole	0.1 mole	0.05 mole
A3	0.003 mole	0.01 mole	0.1 mole	0.05 mole
A5	0.005 mole	0.01 mole	0.1 mole	0.05 mole

2.3. Characterization:

Nanocomposites of PANI-MoS₂ were characterized by UV-Vis spectroscopy, FTIR spectroscopy, XRD analysis and TGA. The DC electrical conductivity was checked by four probe. The experimental details were available from our previous work.

3.RESULTS and DISCUSSION

3.1. UV-Vis Spectra

Figure 1. UV-Visible spectra of selected samples.

Absorbance of selected samples was plotted using UV-Visible spectrometer. The wavelength range was 340-700nm. The two main peaks were obtained at 312nm and at 612nm. The characteristic peaks of pure PANI lies in the range of 280-335 nm and at 638 nm⁴. MoS₂ nanosheets showed characteristic absorption peaks around 600 and 400 nm^{5,6,7}. An absorption maximum at 444.2 nm was observed for MoS₂/PANI composite, when irradiated with UV light, which is in agreement with the absorption phenomena shown by both MoS₂ and PANI, indicating the formation of inorganic-organic nanocomposite. The peak at 312nm may be attributed to π - π^* transition in PANI, it is also related to the extent of conjugation between the adjacent phenyl rings in the polymer chain. The bands around 440 are due to the polaronic transition⁸. The peak at 612nm is due to π -polaron transition between benzenoid and quinoid rings. This absorption band at 612nm is attributed to the quinoid ring transition (charge transfer from HOMO of the benzenoid ring to LUMO of the quinoid ring)⁹. This band is dependent on the overall oxidation state of the polymer.

3.2. FTIR study

Figure 2: FTIR spectra of (a) PANI and (b) PANI-MoS₂nanocomposite.

Table 2: FTIR spectra of the samples.

Peak at cm ⁻¹	Inference
2968	N-H stretching
1628	C=C stretching of quinoid ring
1462	C=C stretching of benzenoid ring
1248	C-N stretching
808	C-H bending

The peak at 1248, 1462 and 1628 cm^{-1} for C-N str, C=C str of benzenoid and C=C str of quinoid rings respectively,¹⁰⁻¹² of PANI-MoS₂, are shifted to lower wavelengths in comparison to PANI, revealing strong interaction between PANI and MoS₂.

3.3. SEM Study

Morphology of PANI and PANI-MoS₂ nanocomposite show that PANI possess fibrillar structure. Morphology of bulk MoS₂ shows sheet like structure. Bulk MoS₂ are agglomerated. The structure of PANI-MoS₂ nanocomposite showed that presence of fibrils of PANI in between the layers of MoS₂, and also on the surface. This led to conclusion, that polymerization under oxidative conditions resulted in forces which exfoliated the layers of MoS₂ and incorporated PANI in between them. This led to an increase in surface area and increase in porosity of MoS₂.

Figure 3: SEM micrographs of (a) PANI (b) MoS₂ (c) PANI-MoS₂ Nanocomposite

3.4. Electrical Conductivity study:

Figure 4: Arrhenius plot of D.C electrical conductivity

DC electrical conductivity of PANI and PANI-MoS₂ nanocomposites and was found to be in the semiconducting range. Increase in the electrical conductivity was observed with the increase in the amount of MoS₂ in the nanocomposites.¹³⁻¹⁵ Similar cases are also reported by Ansari et al. for various nanocomposites based on PANI and zinc oxide nanoparticles Improvement in electrical conductivity of PANI-MoS₂ was observed, which may be due to formation of efficient network of PANI chains and also due to interaction of PANI with MoS₂, which increased the mobility of charge carriers in PANI-MoS₂ nanocomposites leading to increase in electrical conductivity.

3.5. Hydrogen sulphide sensing study:

Sensing H₂S was based on change in electrical conductivity in presence of atmosphere of H₂S vapours. Both PANI and the PANI-MoS₂ nanocomposites showed change in conductivity in an atmosphere of H₂S, but the signals were more pronounced in case of PANI-MoS₂ nanocomposite. The synergism of PANI with MoS₂ exhibited better results. H₂S reacts with -NH of PANI and PANI-MoS₂ nanocomposite, and converts it to HS⁻. H₂S is a weak acid which dissociated into H⁺ and HS⁻. H⁺ partially protonates PANI. This electrical conductivity of PANI and PANI-MoS₂ nanocomposite increases¹⁶. The nanocomposites exhibits improved sensitivity as compared to that of pure PANI. PANI-MoS₂ promotes H₂S absorption due to increased surface area, which allows better absorption of H₂S, and hence the sensing ability.

Figure 5: Chemical sensing of H₂S by (a) PANI and (b) PANI-MoS₂ nanocomposite

4. CONCLUSION:

PANI and the PANI-MoS₂ nanocomposites were prepared by electrochemical polymerization. Formation of nanocomposites was confirmed by FTIR and SEM studies. Sensing studies showed that PANI and PANI-MoS₂ nanocomposites showed excellent sensitivity towards H₂S.

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